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Study and Analysis of Input/Output Analysis to Non Linear Science

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Abstract :

Input-output analysis is a technique invented by Professor Washing W. Leontief in 1951. It is used to analyse inter-industry relationship in order to understand the inter-dependencies and complexities of the economy and thus the conditions for maintain equilibrium between supply and demand. In this research note, we analyse the result of Leontiest and using it to financial sector.

Keywords : Input output analysis, application, surplus, etc.

Introduction :

An industry is the group of firms producing homogenous product and selling or distributing its identical product for the sake and well-being of consumers.

For the production of any particular product an industry has to purchase the required raw materials from the market as well as to hire labour from the market.

It needs to pay the material cost (direct or indirect) purchased from outside, provide wages to the labours, payment for the rent of land, interest on the borrowed capitals. The all acts as an input for the industry and those are processed and takes the borrowed capitals. These all acts as an input for the industry and those are processes and takes the form of output i.e. inputs are processed into outputs.

So, inputs and outputs are the terminology used in the industries. A model which deals or studies abouts are the interrelationship and the interdependency between two industries is input-output model such that the output of one model such that the output of one industry becomes the input of the other industry. The main objectives of the input-output analysis is to deal with the problems such as “what quantity of the output that one industry should produce so that the demand of the consumer satisfy exactly i.e. the volume of production that should be made in order to balance the supply and the demand. The main assumption of the input-output analysis is “the quantity that has produce, should be consumed.”

The term “input-output analysis” is, for well-known reasons, closely associated with the name of Wassily Leontief, input-output analysis may be seen as epitomized by one of the most frequently repeated equation in $X = AX + Y$ many students of Leontief and practitioners of input-output analysis may have reflected upon the almost paradoxical fact that such a general and wide ranging approach as input-output analysis represents, with a strikingly simple and transparent analytic structure.

Discussion :

An important step in the direction was made in an earlier special issue of Economic System Research (Vol. 12, No. 2, 2000) on input-output analysis and classical economic theory. At the Fifteenth International Conference on Input-output Technique, held in Beijing, 27 June-1 July 2006, a special session organized by one of the guest editors of this issue, was devoted to the theme “History of Input-output Analysis”.

Input-output (IO) analysis is a technique that divides the economy into final demand and production and accounts for the direct and indirect interdependencies among different sectors.

The prepared project on “Input-output” analysis has contained some major objective. They are as follow :

1. To find the history of input-output model.
2. To find the nature of input-output model.
3. Determine application of its in real life.
4. To determine the types of input-output model.
5. To learn about Hawkins-Simson condition.

General Two Sector Input-Output Model :

We consider here the interrelationship and interdependency of the economy of two countries.

Introduction	A	B	Final demand	Total output
A	X_{11}	X_{12}	D_1	X_1
B	X_{21}	X_{22}	D_2	X_2

Here,

X_1 = total output of industry A

X_{11} = output of A is taken as input A

X_{21} = output of B is taken as input of A

D_1 = final demand of A

X_2 = total output of industry B

X_{12} = output of A is taken as input of B

X_{22} = output of B is taken as input of B

D_2 = final demand of B

Since, output of A is used as input of A and B and the rest by the external bodies, so Similarly,

A_{11} = input coefficient = x_{11}/x_1 , $a_{12} = x_{12}/x_2$, $a_{21} = x_{21}/x_1$ and $a_{22} = x_{22}/x_2$

So, $x_{11} = a_{11}x_1$, $x_{12} = a_{12}x_2$

$x_{21} = a_{21}x_1$, $x_{22} = a_{22}x_2$

Using the result, we have

$x_{11} = a_{11}x_1 + a_{21}x_2 + d_1$

and $x_2 = a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + d_2$

- $(I - A)x = D$ where I = unit matrix

- If $I - A = T$ be non-singular, then

- $(I - A)^{-1}D = T^{-1}D$

$I - A$ is a matrix known as Leontief's technology matrix or Leontief's matrix only.

Hawkin's Simon Condition :

The condition ensures the viability of the system. The two conditions for viability are as follows :

1. If A = input coefficient matrix and I = unit matrix of same order as that of A , then each diagonal elements of the matrix $I - A$ positive.
2. The determinant of $I - A$ i.e. $I - A$ is positive.

Input-output (IO) analysis is a modeling technique that divides the economy into final demand and production and accounts for the direct and production and accounts for the direct and indirect interdependencies among different sectors.

Some of its example in real world are as follows :

Washing Machine : We select the mode (input) it processes, and our clothes are washed, and we get it automatically washed by the machine (output).

Air-Condition : We select the mode (input), it checks what temperature the mode matches with (process) and we get the results as our room cools (output).

Some inputs might be money, supplies or knowledge, or labor. All of these elements are needed by a company to make products.

It can be further explained from the figure :

Sectors inputs to final total Agriculture manufacturing demand output.

Agriculture	80	320	100	500
Manufacturing	60	40	160	260

The first row shows, the agriculture sectors produces 500 units of outputs in total, of which the majority 320 units flow from the manufacturing sectors as inputs for its production. 100 units are delivered to households directly as final demand, and the remaining 80 units are consumed by the agriculture sectors itself as fodder and seeds.

It is further explained in diagram :

The following inter-industry transactions table was constructed for an economy of the year 2016.

Industry	1	2	Final consumption	Total output
1	500	1600	400	2500
2	1750	1600	4650	8000
Labors	250	4800	-----	-----

Construct technology coefficient matrix showing direct requirements. Does a solution exist for this system.

Solution :

Here, $a_{11} = 500, a_{12} = 1600, x_1 = 2500,$

$a_{21} = 1750, a_{22} = 1600, x_2 = 8000,$

$b_{11} = a_{11}/x_1 = 500/2500 = 0.20,$

$b_{12} = a_{12}/x_2 = 1600/8000 = 0.20,$

$b_{21} = a_{21}/x_1 = 1750/2500 = 0.70,$

$b_{22} = a_{22}/x_2 = 1600/8000 = 0.20.$

The technology matrix is $\begin{bmatrix} 0.2 & 0.2 \\ 0.7 & 0.2 \end{bmatrix}$

Now,

$$|I - B| = \begin{vmatrix} 0.8 & -0.2 \\ -0.7 & 0.8 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (0.8)(0.8) - (0.7)(-0.2) \\
 &= 0.64 - 0.14 \\
 &= 0.50 > 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Since, diagonal elements are positive and $|I - B|$ is positive.

Hawkins-Simon conditions are satisfied. Hence the system has a solution.

In an economy there is production of coal and steel. The table is given below for its data. Do you think that the system is viable? Calculate the gross output of the two commodities and the total labor days required.

	Steel	Coal	Final demand
Steel	0.4	0.1	50
Coal	0.7	0.6	100
Labor days	5	2	-----

The technology matrix is $B = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.1 \\ 0.7 & 0.6 \end{bmatrix}$

As

$$\begin{aligned}
 |I - B| &= \begin{vmatrix} 0.6 & -0.1 \\ -0.7 & 0.4 \end{vmatrix} \\
 &= (0.6)(0.4) - (-0.7)(-0.1) \\
 &= 0.24 - 0.07 \\
 &= 0.1
 \end{aligned}$$

Since, the diagonal elements of $I - B$ are positive and value of $I - B$ is positive, the system is viable.

$$\text{Adj}(I - B) = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.1 \\ 0.7 & 0.6 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$(I - B)^{-1} = \frac{\text{adj}(I - B)}{|I - B|}$$

$$= \frac{1}{0.17} \begin{bmatrix} 0.4 & 0.1 \\ 0.7 & 0.6 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$X = (I - B)^{-1} D, \text{ where } D = \begin{bmatrix} 50 \\ 100 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 176.5 \\ 558.8 \end{bmatrix}$$

Steel Output = 176.5 tones

Coal Output = 558.8 tones

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total labour days required} &= 5(\text{steel output}) + 2(\text{coal output}) \\ &= 5(176.5) + 2(558.8) \\ &= 882.5 + 1117.6 \\ &= 2000 \\ &= 2000 \text{ Labour Days} \end{aligned}$$

Conclusion :

The whole economy is divided into two sectors :

- i) inter-industry sectors and
- ii) final-demand sectors, both being capable of sub-sectoral divisions. The total output of any inter-industry sector is generally capable of being used as inputs by other inter-industry sectors, by itself and by final demand sectors. Prices, consumer demands and factor supplies are given. There are no external economies and diseconomies of production.

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